

Decolorization of malachite green by a novel strain of *Enterobacter*

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Abstract : In this study, we have isolated a novel strain of *Enterobacter* from dye contaminated waste water of West Bengal (Habra) and assessed its capability to remove malachite green (MG), a widely used recalcitrant dye. The dye has been confirmed to be carcinogenic and mutagenic against many organisms. The main objectives of this study were to identify the bacteria, investigate its capability to decolorize malachite green and optimizing the parameters for dye decolorization. The strain was identified to be *Enterobacter asburiae* strain XJUHX-4TM by 16S rRNA gene analyses. The results showed that this strain demonstrated high decolorizing capability (96–99%) at high concentrations of MG (100–1000 mg/L) under shaking condition within 12 h. The optimum temperature and pH range for dye decolorization were found to be 35–40 °C and pH 7–8 respectively. The decolorization activity was found to be dye-concentration and inoculum-volume dependent. As the concentration is increased the organism requires more time and more volume of inoculum for decolorization of the dye from the media. Mineral media containing sucrose as carbon source and beef extract as a nitrogen source serve as the best media for decolorization.

Keywords : Decolorization, *Enterobacter asburiae* strain XJUHX-4TM, malachite green, pH, temperature, inoculum volume, % decolorization.

Introduction

Dyes are widely used in textile, leather tanning, cosmetic, printing, drug and food processing industries. However, most of these dyes are toxic, carcinogenic and hardly biodegradable because of their complex aromatic structure¹. Increase in color fastness and stability have made the process of color removal more difficult. The inefficiency in dyeing process has resulted in 10–15% of unused dyestuff entering the wastewater directly². Removal of dyes from industrial waste waters is of global concern because dyes cause many problems in aqueous environment. Dyes may significantly affect photosynthetic activity in aquatic life because of reduced light penetration and may also be toxic to some aquatic life due to the presence of aromatics, metals, chlorides etc.³.

The triphenylmethane dye malachite green is highly soluble in water and has long been used in the aquaculture industry as a fungicide, parasiticide, and disinfectant⁴. Malachite green is also used extensively for dyeing silk, wool, jute, leather, ceramics and cotton⁵ and as a

cytochemical staining agent⁶. Though used widely, malachite green is highly toxic to mammalian cells^{7,8}, at concentrations as low as 0.1 mg/ml. It also enhances liver tumor formation in rats and causes reproductive abnormalities in rabbits and fishes⁹. Malachite green was recently nominated by the Food and Drug Administration as a priority chemical for carcinogenicity testing by the National Toxicology Program. Therefore, there are both environmental and human health concerns about bioaccumulation of malachite green in terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems.

Several physical and chemical processes have been applied with limited success to remove MG from wastewater; all these were proved to be costly and inefficient, whereas, an eco-friendly, efficient and low cost alternative is the process of bioremediation exploiting microorganisms. Several microorganisms, including bacteria, yeast and fungi have been reported to decolorize various triphenylmethane dyes^{10–17}. In the present study, a bacterial strain, which was isolated from a dye contaminated site

of rural area of West Bengal has been isolated and characterized by analyses of their 16S rRNA gene. The effects of various environmental parameters (pH, temperature, initial dye concentration, and inoculum volume, effects of various carbon and nitrogen sources) on dye decolorization have been optimized.

Materials and methods :

Dyes and chemicals :

The triphenylmethane dye used in this study was Malachite green oxalate (Merck). Samples were centrifuged and then filtered through 0.25 μm membranes to remove bacteria while measuring absorbance. The absorbance was measured with spectrophotometer [UV-Vis spectroscopic analysis (U-4100, Hitachi) at maximum absorption wavelengths $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 617 \text{ nm}$].

Isolation of bacteria :

Water sample was collected from a water body near a small scale dyeing industry, situated at Habra, West Bengal, in the district of North 24-Parganas. Isolated colonies were obtained by serial dilution of the water sample and plating them on medium containing MG. 10 different colonies from the agar plates were screened among which one showed consistent decolorization of MG till 1000 mg/L. This was further studied, identified and effects of media pH, temperature, inoculum volume, various carbon and nitrogen sources on dye decolorization were also analyzed.

Medium used :

After isolating the pure culture of the microorganism, they were grown on nutrient agar (5 g peptone/L, 3 g beef extract/L, 15 g Agar/L, pH 6.8) as well as on nutrient broth medium (5 g peptone/L, 3 g beef extract/L, pH 6.8) and maintained. The bacteria were grown on these media under aerobic condition at 37 °C in a shaker with a speed of 150 rotations per min in case of liquid culture and aerobically in an incubator at 37 °C in case of semi-solid agar culture.

Identification of the strain :

Identification of the selected strain was carried out by performing PCR amplification of its 16S rRNA gene. Genomic DNA from the bacterial species were isolated using bacterial and fungal genomic DNA extraction kit from HiMedia and DNA concentrations were estimated by visual examination of ethidium bromide-stained agarose gels as well as by spectrophotometrical examination.

The 16S rRNA gene was amplified partially with the thermal cycler ABI 9700 (ABI, Foster City, USA). The forward primer used 515F was (5'-3') GTGCCAGC-AGCCGCGGTAA and the reverse primer 1492R was (5'-3') TACGGYTACCTTGTTACGACTT¹⁸. Before amplification cycle DNA was denatured for 2 min at 94 °C and after amplification an extension step (7 min at 72 °C) was performed. The cycling parameters consisted of 28 cycles at : denaturation at 94 °C for 30 s, primer annealing at 45 °C for 1 min, extension at 72 °C for 1 min. The samples were held at 4 °C until analysis by agarose gel electrophoresis. All the amplified PCR products were agarose-gel-eluted using HiMedia gel elution kit. Then the eluted product was sent for sequencing, which was done by MWG-BIOTECH Pvt. Ltd., Sequencing Department, India. The 16S rRNA gene sequence was blast searched against gene bank database. Identification to the species level was determined as a sequence similarity of >99% with that of the prototype strain sequence in the gene bank.

Decolorization study :

For decolorization study, 100 ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 50 ml solution of malachite green prepared in the nutrient broth medium was inoculated with the bacterial strain grown in the liquid medium (log phase culture, O.D₆₀₀ = 1). The flask was kept in a shaking incubator providing aerobic conditions. After decolorization, the decolorized solutions were filtered through 0.25 μm filters and centrifuged at 6000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatants were analyzed spectrophotometrically (617 nm, absorption maxima for malachite green oxalate) using UV-Visible spectrophotometer (U-4100, Hitachi). Each experiment was conducted in duplicate and mean values were taken. For controls, samples containing no bacteria and samples containing no MG were run simultaneously with the experimental samples. The former control was given to see non-specific MG decolorization by components in the medium, while the latter showed the growth of the bacterial strain in media lacking MG.

Decolorization at different initial concentrations of malachite green (100-1000 mg/L) and effect of increasing inoculum percentage on decolorization of malachite green were tested at 37 °C in the nutrient broth. To study the effect of carbon and nitrogen sources on decolorization of malachite green, semi-synthetic medium having

following composition was used (g/L) : MG : 0.1, KH₂PO₄ : 1, KCl : 0.5, NaNO₃ : 2, MgSO₄.7H₂O : 0.5, FeSO₄.7H₂O : 0.01, with different carbon (glucose, lactose, maltose, sucrose, 1.5% each) and nitrogen (peptone, yeast extract, malt extract, beef extract, 0.3% each) sources. Effects of temperature (15–50 °C), initial medium pH (3.0–10.0) on the degradation of MG were studied.

The percentage decolorization was calculated as follows :

$$\% \text{ Decolorization} = [(\text{Initial absorbance} - \text{Observed absorbance}) / \text{Initial absorbance}] \times 100$$

Results and discussion

Analyses of 16S rRNA gene :

The 16S rRNA gene sequence of the species was submitted at GenBank under Accession No. HQ830346. Comparison with available sequences in GenBank showed very high similarity to organism HQ830346 with that of *Enterobacter asburiae* and the strain was designated as *Enterobacter asburiae* strain XJUHX-4TM. A phylogenetic tree based on known representatives of related species is presented in Fig. 1.

MG decolorization :

When studied, it was found out that the bacteria, *Enterobacter asburiae* strain XJUHX-4TM was able to decolorize 98% of the dye from the media when the dye concentration is 100 mg/L within 4 h and no further change in decolorization takes place till 24 h. As the initial dye concentration increases the required time for decolorization also gets increased (Fig. 2a). When the dye concentrations were 500 and 1000 mg/L, it required 7 h and 12 h respectively for complete decolorization of the dye solution. Parshetti *et al.*¹² has described MG decolorization by *Kocuria rosea* within 5 h in anoxic and static condition, when the concentration was 50 mg/L. However, no decolorization was obtained in aerobic condition. Li *et al.*¹³ worked on *Pseudomonas* sp. and the strain requires 12 h to decolorize 90% of the dye (50 mg/L). Govindwar and Jadav¹⁹ showed *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* MTCC 463 decolorized MG (100 mg/L) containing media within 7 h. Our isolate, strain XJUHX-4TM decolorizes 100 mg/L MG containing media within 4 h. Therefore, the strain XJUHX-4TM can be considered as a more efficient decolorizer of MG.

Fig. 1. Dendrogram illustrating the (16S rDNA gene) similarity of the bacteria HQ830346 to strains exhibiting highest sequence similarity.

Fig. 2a. Effect of initial dye concentration and required time on decolorization of the dye malachite green : (♦) % decolorization, (■) time (h).

Effect of temperature and pH :

Determination of temperature requirements of microorganisms used for this purpose is important since temperature requirements above ambient ranges may require an energy input and hence not cost-effective. This organism can carry on decolorization over a broad temperature range (25–40 °C). The optimum temperature for the removal of the dye was found to be in the range of 35–40 °C (Fig. 2b), which is almost the normal range of temperature in tropical country like India (except for winter). Hence this can be considered as an efficient, cost-effective decolorizer of dye contaminated waste water in these regions. Temperature below 20 °C reduces the efficiency of dye decolorization. An increase or reduction in temperature above or below the range may lead to inactivation of the microbial enzymes, which, in turn, may slow down the decolorization process.

Fig. 2b. Effect of temperature on dye decolorization by *E. asburiae* strain XJUHX-4TM.

The effect of MG decolorization was analyzed over pH range from 3.0 to 10.0. It was observed that the amount of dye removed varies with pH. Maximum decolorization was obtained between media pH of 6–8 (Fig. 2c), which remains almost same after the complete decolori-

Fig. 2c. Effect of pH on dye decolorization by *E. asburiae* strain XJUHX-4TM.

zation process. At both pH 7 and 8, the decolorization was almost 98%. pH 7 is also the optimum pH for the growth of the organism and this indicates that the microorganism may be utilizing the dye as one of its substrate and probably the dye is being degraded by the microorganisms for their growth. At pH lower than bacterial isoelectric point (pI) (the pI of *Enterobacter* may lie somewhat close to pI 2.5–3 considering pI of other members of Gram-negative Enterobacteriaceae family²¹), the surface of bacterium carries a positive charge (McCalla and Clark)²², thereby may hinder the approach of the positively charged MG molecule, resulting in the observed decrease in decolorization efficiency. At a pH higher than the isoelectric point, the surface of the bacterium changes to negatively charged, which results in an increased electrostatic attractive force between the bacterial cell and the positively charged MG molecule and accounts for higher decolorization efficiency of the organism as pH is increased²⁰. It is to be noted the increased decolorization efficiency at pH 8 is an indication that the organism can be considered as an efficient one for treating dye contaminated wastewater, as most industrial dyes are basic in nature.

Effect of different carbon and nitrogen source on decolorization :

The efficacy of *E. asburiae* strain XJUHX-4TM to decolorize 100 mg/L of MG in the presence of different

culture conditions was tested in order to obtain efficient and faster decolorization. In the mineral medium 60% decolorization was observed within 4 h and no further decolorization was observed. The decolorization observed in presence of 1.5% glucose, sucrose, maltose and lactose were 65, 82, 68 and 35% respectively (Fig. 2d). In presence of 1.5% sucrose, 99% MG decolorization was observed within 4 h when beef extract was used as nitrogen source. Decolorization efficiency gradually decreased when yeast extract (80%), peptone (58%), and malt extract (52%) were used (Fig. 2e). The result indicates that the beef extract, along with sucrose promotes the bacterial decolorization activity. As both of the components are well known nutrient sources for microorganisms, therefore, it can be concluded that both of the sources may accelerate bacterial growth, which in turn accelerates bacterial dye decolorization activity.

Fig. 2d. Effect of different carbon source on decolorization (dye conc. 100 mg/L).

Fig. 2e. Effect of different nitrogen source on decolorization in presence of 1.5% sucrose (dye conc. 100 mg/L).

Effect of inoculum concentration :

As the inoculum concentration of *E. asburiae* was increased, the decolorization rate of MG (100 mg/L) was also increased. With 1, 2, 5 and 10% inoculum the time required to achieve 98% decolorization of MG was 24, 20, 8, 4 h respectively. Larger the concentration of the

dye, larger volume of inoculum it demands. When 1000 mg/L MG was used, the inoculum volume increased to 15%, whereas, % decolorization remained unchanged (98%) in case of 100 mg/L of the dye, even if 15% inoculum was added (Fig. 2f). This seems to indicate that the optimum inoculum volume is in the range of 10–15% of the whole media when dye concentration ranges from 100–1000 mg/L.

Fig. 2f. Effect of inoculum concentration on dye decolorization : (•) % decolorization at 100 mg/L, (■) % decolorization at 1000 mg/L.

Conclusion :

The present study revealed the ability of *E. asburiae* XJUH4-4TM to decolorize MG which is a novel strain to be studied in this field. The results showed that the decolorization depends on : temperature, pH, dye concentration, initial inoculum size and media composition. The maximum decolorization took place at temperature between 35–40 °C. The optimal media pH for decolorization is pH 8. Presence of 0.3% beef extract along with 1.5% sucrose stimulates the process of dye decolorization. Therefore, it can be urged that the strain we have isolated is a good potential candidates for degradation of malachite green.

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